

FURTHER DEVELOPING A CULTURE OF COOPERATION TO HIGHER EDUCATION STUDENTS WITH THE HELP OF "CLUSTER" METHODOLOGY

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Annotation.

In this article, the "Cluster" method is based on the knowledge and skills needed to acquire new information, to form new thinking skills or to improve existing thinking skills, to moderate interpersonal relationships, to find a solution to a real problem. considerations have been made

Keywords.

Cluster, model, principle, mechanism, component, algorithm

The fact that we chose this model as a priority for the implementation of cluster interaction is explained by the fact that the model is focused on the student: "With this approach, the developing characteristics of the student become the highest value for the teacher. His person is treated with respect and sympathy. The goal of education and upbringing is aimed at forming personal values necessary for the future specialist to adapt to the world around him independently" [1].

The principles of the cluster interaction process developed by D. Renzulli are also important for us:

1. Pays attention to practical application of learned material, development of skills.
2. Students and teachers independently choose the groups they want to join.
3. Brings students from different groups and courses into groups with similar interests.
4. Lack of a clear plan or schedule.
5. Manage clusters using reliable methods and advanced information and materials similar to creative experts and researchers.
6. Provides multiple talent development opportunities through division of labor within the cluster.

7. Reserves specific blocks of time for cluster implementation.
8. Excludes the principles of traditional educational institutions” [2]

The essence of the indicated principles is that the interaction of the cluster, if it occurs, serves to implement the mechanisms of self-organization of the subjects participating in it.

In addition to creating a trusting situation in the community, the student body united by self-interest formed what scholars call a "self-sustaining chain of division." Many essential components require essential particles to perform at peak performance. It should be noted that the common interests of cluster members not only minimize personal differences, but also contribute to more mutually creative relations.

The effect of "change of values" is manifested in the realization of the value of the production activity by a number of participants of the creative process of the group and changes in the parameters of their behavior and mental activity after this implementation [3]

The freedom to choose the topic of research, conditions, methods of work, partners helps to increase the personal responsibility of each group and the group as a whole for the result of joint activity, thereby triggering the mechanisms of self-organization. As a result of self-organization of mutual cooperation, it is necessary to coordinate the actions of all its subjects and create reliable mutual support relations between them.

At the same time, while organizing the mutual cooperation of the cluster, it is necessary to understand that the state of freedom of activity in the cluster creates the ground not only for the creative nature of cooperation and the emergence of innovative ideas, but also for the emergence of contradictions between clusters. Interpersonal conflicts resulting from the breakdown of cooperation represent a potential conflict area.

The experience of the emergence and resolution of conflicts that inevitably arise in the course of cluster interaction helps to make the most effective group decision, prevents stagnation of relations and enriches the personal resource of constructive conflict resolution. This, in turn, increases the educational level of the culture of cooperation between the cluster subjects.

Thus, during theoretical research, we came to the conclusion that cluster interaction has an important pedagogical potential for the development of a culture of cooperation among students.

It should be emphasized once again that the potential of cluster cooperation as a means of developing a culture of cooperation in the student community is

realized if the cooperation process organized within the higher education educational cluster is characterized by the following components: collective trust, disorder in cooperation (unstructured exchange of ideas), constructive attitude - resistance includes understanding the cultural continuity of interaction in the formation of qualitatively new and socially significant values.

In order to develop a culture of cooperation in the student community, the algorithm of interaction of the following groups will be developed:

- researching the interests of members in cluster interactions;
- to research and analyze the main topics of the cluster;
- implementation of the cluster;
- the transparency of the process due to the interaction of the cluster;
- reflection and assessment of cluster interaction efficiency, etc.

As a means of developing a culture of cooperation in the student community of higher education institutions, it is possible to determine the basics of the theoretical analysis of the possibilities of clusters in mutual relations:

- directing the goal of education to the formation of individual qualities and values necessary for independent adaptation of future personnel to the world around them;

- in the process of promotion and implementation of ideas, by increasing the socio-spiritual potential and opportunities of the participants of mutual cooperation, creating synergy effectiveness;

- ensuring independent selection of research conditions, methods, topics and cooperation of teams, which creates the basis for increasing the responsibility of each individual for the result of joint activity;

- to provide each member of the cluster with the opportunity to actively participate in the development of their specialization and reflection of their views through "making a significant contribution to the organization of the whole" or "division of labor" (distribution of powers);

- permanent confidentiality and free exchange of information;

- people;

- there is no need to update the mechanisms of self-organization of the movement and control the interaction process from the outside.

After studying scientific studies, we came to the conclusion that the term "cluster" is used as a general concept that includes all the elements of the theory of cluster development.

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